

Occurrence of multiple flame fronts in reheat combustors

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Abstract

Reheat flames are mainly stabilized by autoignition processes. In this paper their unsteady response to temperature fluctuations is investigated. To this end, a simple one dimensional duct is considered as an analytic surrogate model of a reheat combustion chamber. A chemistry-based correlation for the autoignition delay time is used to predict the flame position. In order to analyze the flame response to temperature fluctuations, the inlet boundary condition is harmonically excited. Depending on the amplitude and frequency of excitation, nonlinear phenomena are observed, in particular the co-existence of multiple flame fronts at different axial locations. The analytic formulation of the problem allows us to predict the onset of nonlinearities and to evaluate maps separating the linear from the nonlinear behavior, as function of the system parameters. Amplitude and frequency thresholds triggering different nonlinear properties of the system are identified. Verification of the obtained results for different excitation states is made by comparison to previously conducted Large Eddy Simulations of a simplified reheat combustor geometry represented by a backward-facing step. The simplified model is able to correctly predict the appearance of nonlinear phenomena as observed in the simulations suggesting that the governing factors are well represented.

Keywords: Temperature fluctuations, autoignition flames, multiple flames, nonlinearities, entropy waves

1. Introduction

Modern gas turbines need to fulfill increasingly strict limitations in terms of pollutant emissions and at the same time guarantee high efficiency and operational flexibility. Ansaldo Energia GT26 and GT36 gas turbines address these challenges by means of a sequential combustion system in which two combustion stages are arranged in series [1, 2, 3, 4]. The first stage lean-premix combustor is aerodynamically stabilized, whereas the second stage relies mainly on autoignition to stabilize the flame. Burning in lean conditions requires particular attention during the design phase to avoid a potential coupling between the acoustic field and the dynamic flame response, i.e. the possible onset of thermoacoustic instabilities. Most of the literature on thermoacoustics is dedicated to the thermoacoustics of premixed propagating flames [5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10, 11]. Recently, reheat flames are gaining more and more interest due to their increasing relevance in gas turbine development.

Propagation stabilized flames are mainly sensitive to velocity and equivalence ratio fluctuations [12]. In contrast to this, different works have demonstrated that autoignition flames are instead more susceptible to temperature and pressure fluctuations [13, 14]. Zellhuber *et al.* [15, 16] investigate the effect of pressure fluctuations on heat release rate, especially in the high frequency domain. An

analytic model for the flame transfer function is derived. System stability is studied in a linear framework and nonlinear effects are modeled in terms of flame describing function. The importance of temperature fluctuations is not considered.

Yang *et al.* [17] perform Large Eddy Simulations (LES) to identify flame transfer functions. Equivalence ratio and temperature perturbations are shown to have a major effect on the dynamic flame response. Additionally, network models are used to predict system thermoacoustics. The analysis is restricted to the linear behavior. This work has been extended by Scarpato *et al.* [13] and Bothien *et al.* [14], who study and identify the flame as a MISO and a MIMO system, respectively. In both works, the key role of pressure and temperature fluctuations is highlighted. In [14], a dedicated analysis is conducted to determine the limits of linearity of the flame response.

Recently Aditya *et al.* [18] perform direct numerical simulations of a backward-facing step reheat combustor. The chemical explosive mode analysis is used to identify autoignition dominated and propagation dominated regions in the flame. Also Schultz *et al.* [19, 20] investigate the presence of propagation and autoignition regions in the flame by means of LES. The nonlinear regime is explored and it is shown that nonlinear effects can appear already at relatively low excitation levels.

Fleck *et al.* [21, 22, 23] perform experimental autoignition studies of a reheat combustor operated with vitiated air and a hydrogen/nitrogen mixture. Experiments are performed at typical gas turbines reheat combustor oper-

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ating pressure, velocities and temperatures. Limits of ignition and autoignition delay times are measured and the appearance of ignition flame-stabilizing kernels is studied. The results are compared with numerical simulations and temperature is found in both cases to be the dominant factor. The presence of autoignition kernels in the mixing duct has been observed by Aditya *et al.* [18] and Schultz *et al.* [20], as well.

The important role of temperature fluctuations, often also referenced to as entropy waves, for the stability of a thermoacoustic system has been widely investigated in literature but almost solely for propagation stabilized flames [24, 25, 26, 27]. Eckstein *et al.* [24] perform experiments to assess the impact of entropy waves on low frequency thermoacoustic instabilities of aero-engines. In Giusti *et al.* [25], propagation, dissipation and reflection of entropy waves are analyzed numerically and experimentally. A low-order model of the mechanism is proposed and validated. Li *et al.* [26] tackle the effect of entropy waves on the stability of a thermoacoustic system. It is shown that choked outlet conditions can amplify by up to three orders of magnitude the energy of acoustic disturbances. Recent works on indirect noise show that also compositional inhomogeneities can generate entropy waves [27, 28].

In this paper, we investigate a nonlinear effect that we observed in numerical simulations of reheat flames [14]: the simultaneous appearance of multiple flame fronts at different axial locations caused by forcing the flame with temperature fluctuations. We develop a simple analytic model able to capture its features and predict its occurrence. The obtained results are compared with LES simulations to verify their correctness and accuracy.

The remainder of this article is organized as follows. Section §2 introduces the observed phenomena and provides a physical explanation. An analytic formulation of the problem is derived. Section §3 studies the analytic model, identifying the transition conditions from a single flame system to a multiple flames system. Maps of system behavior are provided based on detailed chemistry calculations. Section §4 defines the numerical setup used to validate the results of §3 and shows comparisons between LES and model predictions. Conclusions are drawn in Section §5.

2. Problem definition

We consider a one dimensional duct filled with fuel and air that are perfectly mixed. The position along the duct is described by the coordinate $x \in [0, +\infty)$, where $x = 0$ is the duct inlet. We assume the presence of mean flow in positive x -direction with velocity \bar{u} . Static properties of the fluid, i.e. temperature \bar{T} , pressure \bar{p} and density $\bar{\rho}$ are assumed to be constant. The temperature \bar{T} is assumed to be sufficiently high to cause autoignition in the mixture. The autoignition delay time, τ , is defined as the time necessary for a mixture to ignite in the absence of external perturbations to the system e.g., a spark. τ is

a complex function of the mixture composition, pressure and temperature. In the following, we consider only the dependence of τ on the temperature, i.e. $\tau = \tau(T)$, assuming in addition to a uniform mixture composition also uniform pressure.

Given the high temperature, the chemical reactions are initiated already at the entrance of the mixture into the duct and continue while the fuel is convected downstream. When the autoignition delay time equals the residence time of the mixture in the duct the fuel ignites and a flame is observed at an axial position $x_{\text{fl}} = \bar{u}\tau(\bar{T})$. For most fuels used in gas turbines, the autoignition delay time $\tau(T)$ is a monotonically decreasing function of the temperature, i.e.:

$$\frac{d\tau}{dT} < 0 \quad (1)$$

Higher temperatures result in faster chemical reactions and shift the flame position closer to the inlet, the opposite happens for lower temperatures. This is in accordance with the Arrhenius law, which suggests a reaction rate dependence on mixture properties given by:

$$k = Ae^{-\frac{E_A}{RT}} \quad (2)$$

where k is the reaction rate, A and E_A mixture and pressure dependent constants, R the universal gas constant and T the mixture temperature. For some exceptional fuels and/or conditions the autoignition delay time non-monotonically depends on temperature [29, 30, 31]. In the present work this is excluded.

Since the aim of the present work is to study the flame response to temperature fluctuations we introduce a perturbation in the inlet temperature $T(x = 0, t)$. In particular, we describe it according to a sinusoidal wave with angular frequency ω and amplitude ΔT :

$$T(x = 0, t) = \bar{T} + \Delta T \cos(\omega t) \quad (3)$$

This condition corresponds to alternating hot and cold spots convected downstream. We know from Eq. (1) that for a hot spot the chemistry evolves faster and ignition occurs earlier; the flame moves upstream. In contrast to this cold spots take more time to ignite and consequently result in a flame position located more downstream. As hot and cold spots alternate, the flame oscillates around the mean position $x_{\text{fl}} = \bar{u}\tau(\bar{T})$. When the temperature reaches its maximum $T_{\text{max}} = \bar{T} + \Delta T$, the autoignition delay time $\tau(T_{\text{max}})$ will be minimum and the flame will be located at $x_{\text{fl}} = \bar{u}\tau(T_{\text{max}})$, and vice versa when the temperature is at its minimum $T_{\text{min}} = \bar{T} - \Delta T$. This is visualized in Fig. 1. For sufficiently large ΔT , a nonlinear phenomenon appears: multiple flame fronts coexist at different axial locations. This is presented in Fig. 2. The physical explanation for this phenomenon is that the downstream cold mixture still needs time to autoignite, whereas the upstream hot mixture, even if injected in the duct at a later time, has already started to burn. Therefore, three flame

fronts are visible at the same time instant. This effect can occur only if the temperature amplitude ΔT is sufficiently large so as to make τ_{\min} and τ_{\max} substantially different from each other.

In the following, this will be cast in a mathematical formulation. The perturbation of inlet temperature $T(x = 0, t)$ is convected downstream by the mean flow and results in a temperature function that depends on both time and space, in particular:

$$T(x, t) = \bar{T} + \Delta T \cos(\omega(x/\bar{u} - t)) \quad (4)$$

We assume thermal diffusion to be negligible. Additionally we consider the flow field composed of a series of independently evolving plug flows, each one convected downstream with the velocity \bar{u} . Since the autoignition delay τ is a function of the temperature, we can define an autoignition delay field accordingly:

$$\tau = \tau(T) = \tau(T(x, t)) = \tau(\bar{T} + \Delta T \cos(\omega(x/\bar{u} - t))) \quad (5)$$

Each section has a different temperature T and a corresponding autoignition delay time $\tau(T)$. When its autoignition delay time equals its residence time in the duct $t_{\text{res}} = x/\bar{u}$ the mixture burns and a flame is observed. This condition can be expressed mathematically as:

$$\tau(T(x, t)) = \tau(\bar{T} + \Delta T \cos(\omega(x/\bar{u} - t))) = x/\bar{u} \quad (6)$$

If one assumes that the autoignition delay temporal dependence on the temperature can be described by an Arrhenius-like equation, $\tau(T) = A \exp(\Theta/T)$, then Eq. (6) becomes:

$$A \exp\left(\frac{\Theta}{\bar{T} + \Delta T \cos(\omega(x/\bar{u} - t))}\right) = x/\bar{u} \quad (7)$$

For a fixed time instant t , Eq. (7) is a nonlinear algebraic equation in the domain $x \in [0, +\infty)$. Its solutions correspond to the flame fronts positions x_{fl} at that time t . We want to analyze for which conditions the equation presents multiple solutions, i.e. which are the necessary conditions for the presence of multiple flame fronts. We present in Figs. 1 and 2, Eq. (6) for a fixed time instant t . Intersections between the time delay curve and the residence time line correspond to the flame positions. The axial positions where a flame can be observed are limited by the maximum excursion of the autoignition delay time $\tau(T) \in [\tau_{\min}, \tau_{\max}]$.

3. Modelling of the flame front dynamics

3.1. Change of variables

We want to find the number of solutions of Eq. (6) for each time instant t . This is equivalent to finding the number of zeros of the function $f(x, t)$ defined as:

$$\begin{aligned} f(x, t) &= \tau(T(x, t)) - x/\bar{u} \\ &= \tau(\bar{T} + \Delta T \cos(\omega(x/\bar{u} - t))) - x/\bar{u} \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

Figure 1: Temperature fluctuations effect on the flame position, linear regime. In the top three plots we present, for three subsequent time instances, the temperature wave in the duct, with respective flame position. In the bottom figure we plot the corresponding delay wave $\tau(x, t)$ and its intersection (cross) with the residence time τ_{res} . As the time evolves the wave $\tau(x, t)$ shifts to the right and the cross, i.e. the flame front, moves accordingly. The bold rectangular box $[u\tau_{\min}, u\tau_{\max}] \times [\tau_{\min}, \tau_{\max}]$ highlighted represents the maximum flame front position excursion.

The $2\pi/\omega$ periodicity of the problem allows us to restrict the mathematical domain to $[x, t] \in [u\tau_{\min}, u\tau_{\max}] \times [-2\pi/\omega + \tau_{\min}, +\tau_{\min}]$. We introduce the change of variables:

$$X = x/u - t \quad (9a)$$

$$Y = -t + \tau_{\min} \quad (9b)$$

The new domain of the problem is given by $X \in [0, \tau_{\max} - \tau_{\min} + 2\pi/\omega]$ and $Y \in [0, 2\pi/\omega]$. The function $f(x, t)$ in Eq. (8) is replaced by:

$$\begin{aligned} F(X, Y) &= \tau(\bar{T} + \Delta T \cos(\omega X)) - X - \tau_{\min} + Y \\ &= F_x(X) - F_y(Y) \end{aligned} \quad (10a)$$

$$F_x(X) \triangleq \tau(\bar{T} + \Delta T \cos(\omega X)) - X - \tau_{\min} \quad (10b)$$

$$F_y(Y) \triangleq -Y \quad (10c)$$

Equation (10) is better suited than Eq. (8) to study the problem, because it decouples the spatial dependence X from the temporal dependence Y . In fact we can plot the

Figure 2: Temperature fluctuations effect on the flame position, non-linear regime. We present, for a given time instant, the multiple flame condition. On the top plot three flame fronts are visible. The first is in direct contact with the fresh mixture flow, whereas the second and the third are separated by a pocket of unburnt gases. The bottom plot present the delay wave $\tau(x, t)$ corresponding to the temperature wave $T(x, t)$ of the top plot. The intersections with the residence time τ_{res} are marked with crosses and represent the flame locations. The multiple flame front condition is possible because the amplitude ΔT of the temperature wave Eq. (3) is larger than in Fig. 1.

function $F_x(X)$ in the domain $X \in [0, \tau_{max} - \tau_{min} + 2\pi/\omega]$ without choosing any value for Y , a scaled version of the time t . Afterwards we intersect the function $F_x(X)$ with the horizontal lines $F_y(Y) = -Y$ with $Y \in [0, 2\pi/\omega]$. The number of intersections between the two curves is the number of flames present in the system. This number changes as the time Y changes from 0 to $2\pi/\omega$. This is presented in Fig. 3.

3.2. Critical temperature amplitudes

Figure 3 is particularly useful to understand the condition of multiple flame fronts occurrence. In fact, $F_x(X)$ and $F_y(Y)$ can have multiple intersections only if $F_x(X)$ exhibits a region where its first derivative is positive. It can be shown, see Appendix A, that a necessary and sufficient condition for the existence of multiple flame fronts is that there are $\bar{X} \in [0, 2\pi/\omega]$ so that:

$$\left. \frac{dF_x(X)}{dX} \right|_{\bar{X}} = \left. \frac{\partial F(X, Y)}{\partial X} \right|_{\bar{X}} > 0 \quad (11)$$

Since the function $F_x(X)$ depends nonlinearly on the two parameters ΔT and ω , different combinations of their values can change the system properties so that Eq. (11) is fulfilled or not. For the moment, we assume to fix ω and study the system properties as ΔT increases. For small ΔT the function $\tau(\bar{T} + \Delta T \cos(\omega X))$ will be approximately equal to the constant $\tau(\bar{T})$ and therefore

$F_x(X) \approx \tau(\bar{T}) - X - \tau_{min}$. In this small ΔT regime, $F_x(X)$ is linear and only one intersection with the line $F_y(Y) = -Y$ is possible. The system is described by a single flame oscillating slightly around its mean position $\bar{x}_f = \bar{u}\tau(\bar{T})$. As ΔT increases the nonlinear character of $F_x(X)$ becomes more and more pronounced, up to the condition for which Eq. (11) is satisfied. We denote with ΔT_{c1} a first critical temperature amplitude representing the smallest ΔT for which Eq. (11) is satisfied. This is the minimum theoretical value of temperature fluctuations necessary to observe double flames, for a fixed angular frequency ω .

It can be shown, see Appendix A, that there is an upper bound for ΔT_{c1} , which is given by the solution of:

$$\tau_{max} u - \tau_{min} u = \frac{\pi}{\omega} u \quad (12)$$

A physical understanding of Eq. (12) is provided in Fig. 4. The left hand side of Eq. (12) represents the maximum excursion of the flame position, i.e. the width of the rectangular box that is the mathematical domain of our problem. The right hand side is half the wavelength of the delay wave Eq. (5). Note that the delay wave is not sinusoidal anymore because of the nonlinearity of $\tau(T)$ (Eq. (7)), nevertheless it is $2\pi/\omega$ periodic and the concept of wavelength is well defined. Equation (12) is of interest because its solution is an upper bound for the solution of Eq. (11), i.e. Eq. (11) is always satisfied when Eq. (12) is satisfied. We define $\Delta T_{1/2}$ as the temperature fluctuation at which Eq. (12) becomes true. We can generalize the concept and define ΔT_N as the value of temperature fluctuations necessary for Eq. (13) to be valid:

$$\tau_{max} u - \tau_{min} u = 2N \frac{\pi}{\omega} u \quad (13)$$

N is the number of wavelengths the delay wave comprises in the domain $u(\tau_{max} - \tau_{min})$. Equation (12), for example, is the specialization of Eq. (13) to the condition $N = 1/2$.

If we continue to increase the temperature fluctuation ΔT , we will reach a condition when multiple flames are present in the system for each time instant. We define the temperature excitation necessary to observe this condition as second critical temperature fluctuation amplitude, ΔT_{c2} . This is a very peculiar condition because once ΔT_{c2} is exceeded it is not anymore possible to observe a single flame. The mathematical expression reads:

$$F_x(X_M) - F_x(X_m) \geq \frac{2\pi}{\omega} \quad (14)$$

where we introduced the coordinate X_m of the relative minimum of $F_x(X)$ in $[0, 2\pi/\omega]$ and X_M of the relative maximum. This is visualized in Fig. 5: if and only if each horizontal line $F_y(Y) = -Y$, $Y \in [0, 2\pi/\omega]$ intersects the curve $F_x(X)$ more than once, then there are multiple flame fronts for each time instant Y . This happens only if the vertical separation between the maximum and the minimum of $F_x(X)$ is larger than $2\pi/\omega$.

It can be shown that $\Delta T_{N=1}$ and $\Delta T_{N=3/2}$ are respectively lower and upper bounds of ΔT_{c2} .

Figure 3: Autoignition flame front diagram as function of the temperature wave characteristic. We present $F_x(X)$ and $F_y(Y)$ from Eq. (10). $F_x(X)$ is given by a periodic term $\tau(\bar{T} + \Delta T \cos(\omega X)) - \tau_{\min}$ and by a linear term $-X$. The effect of the magnitude of temperature fluctuations ΔT on $F_x(X)$ is shown. The functions $F_y(Y)$ are horizontal lines spanning $F_y(Y) = 0$ to $F_y(Y) = -2\pi/\omega$. Each line represents a different time instant. The intersections (crosses) between $F_x(X)$ and $F_y(Y)$ represent the flames, whose number and position change with time.

3.3. Results summary

We summarize results of Section §3.2. We start from a condition without excitation of the inlet temperature $T(x=0, t)$, i.e. $\Delta T = 0$. In this condition, the flame is stagnant and positioned at $x_{fl} = \bar{u}\tau(\bar{T})$. As we increase the amplitude of excitation (for a given frequency) we observe the following situations, visualized by Fig. 6:

- I For small ΔT , there is only one flame in the system, oscillating linearly around the position $x_{fl} = \bar{u}\tau(\bar{T})$.
- II Increasing ΔT at a certain point satisfies Eq. (11). This will be the first time we observe multiple flame fronts in the system. These flames are present during a period of oscillation for just a limited amount of time.
- III For larger values of the temperature fluctuation ΔT , Eq. (12) will be satisfied. Its solution is an upper bound for the solution of Eq. (11).
- IV Larger values of ΔT cause the wavelength of the delay wave to match the length of the domain i.e., we reach

Eq. (13) with $N = 1$. This condition is a lower bound for Eq. (14). Note that increasing ΔT will increase the percentage of the period of the system in which multiple flame fronts are present.

- V Further increasing ΔT we will satisfy Eq. (14). From now on there is always more than one flame in the system. The number of flames increases with increasing ΔT .
- VI The last condition is given by Eq. (13) with $N = 3/2$. This condition is an upper bound for the solution of Eq. (14) which guarantees multiple flame fronts for each time t .

Note that $\Delta T_{1/2}$, ΔT_1 and $\Delta T_{3/2}$ are not equispaced, because of the nonlinearity of the function $\tau(T)$ in T .

Results presented as a function of the temperature fluctuation ΔT for a given angular frequency ω hold equally if we fix the temperature fluctuation ΔT and instead increase the angular frequency ω from a condition $\omega = 0$. We can introduce naturally three new quantities: ω_{c1} , ω_{c2} and ω_N . ω_{c1} is the first critical ω , i.e. the smallest value

Figure 4: Effect of temperature waves amplitude on the number of flames. We present on the horizontal axis the position x along the duct and on the vertical axis the autoignition delay time τ . The blue curve is the autoignition delay wave $\tau(t, x)$ at a given time instant, the orange line is the residence time line in the duct. The highlighted rectangular box represents the maximum flame front position excursion. $uN\pi/\omega$ is $N/2$ times the wavelength of the delay wave $\tau(x, t)$. The box length in the right, middle and left frames match half, one and one and a half times the wavelength of the delay wave $\tau(x, t)$ respectively, corresponding to Eq. (13) with $N = 1/2$, $N = 1$ and $N = 3/2$.

Figure 5: Autoignition flame front diagram as function of the temperature wave characteristic. We present the functions $F_x(X)$ and $F_y(Y)$. The functions $F_y(Y)$ are horizontal lines spanning $F_y(Y) = 0$ to $F_y(Y) = -2\pi/\omega$ and represent the evolving time. Intersections (crosses) between $F_x(X)$ and $F_y(Y)$ represent the flame in the system at each time step. In order to always have at least more than one intersection, i.e. at least more than one flame, the difference between the maximum and minimum of $F_x(X)$ in the interval $[0, 2\pi/\omega]$ must be greater or equal to $2\pi/\omega$. This is the graphical interpretation of Eq. (14).

of ω for which Eq. (11) is satisfied. It represents the minimum ω necessary to have multiple flame fronts. ω_{c2} is the second critical ω , i.e. the smallest value of ω for which

Eq. (14) is satisfied. It represents the minimum ω necessary to have multiple flame fronts at each time instant. ω_N is the angular frequency ω necessary to satisfy Eq. (13) for

Figure 6: Characteristic regions of flame occurrences as a function of temperature excitation amplitude. As the temperature fluctuation amplitude ΔT increases the system behavior changes. We present the first and second critical temperature amplitudes and the corresponding lower and upper bounds. Note that $\Delta T_{1/2}$, ΔT_1 and $\Delta T_{3/2}$ are not equispaced because of the nonlinearity of the function $\tau(T)$. For small excitation temperatures, in the regime labeled as I (blue, solid line), the system presents a single flame front. In the regimes II-III-IV (red, dashed line) multiple flame fronts can be observed for part of the oscillation period. Very large temperature fluctuations, regions V-VI (yellow, dash-dot line), make multiple flames be present at all time instants.

a given N .

3.4. Linear and nonlinear regimes

We can make use of the theoretical results of Section §3.2 to compute maps of the system behavior for varying ω and ΔT . Computations are based on the GRI 3.0 mechanism [32] and consider methane as fuel. For all presented figures we consider the same mixture composition and pressure.

Results will be presented with respect to a nondimensionalized version of the angular frequency ω , the Strouhal number St defined as:

$$St \triangleq \frac{\omega S}{u} \quad (15)$$

where S is a reference length and u is a reference velocity.

The excitation frequency in Fig. 7 is fixed and numerically shows how the system passes from one flame regime to the multiple flames regime. One notices that $\Delta T_{1/2}$ is an upper bound for ΔT_{c1} and that ΔT_{c2} is always bounded between ΔT_1 and $\Delta T_{3/2}$. Additionally we discover that low inlet temperatures promote multiple flame fronts due to the increasing sensitivity of $\tau(T)$ on T .

In Fig. 8, we present results for the first critical temperature as a function of the inlet temperature and the excitation frequency. We observe that systems with high excitation frequencies and low inlet temperatures are more prone to show multiple flame conditions. Nevertheless one must consider that for too low inlet temperatures the pure autoignition model for the flame dynamics is not accurate anymore, since propagation effects start to play a role. Additionally, for high frequencies the thermal diffusion becomes more and more pronounced and cannot be neglected anymore. This is also shown in [14], where the temperature transfer function of a burner clearly presents a low pass behavior that attenuates inlet temperature disturbances before they reach the flame.

In sections §3.2 and §3.3 we introduced ΔT_{c1} and ω_{c1} . The first one is determined fixing the angular frequency of the perturbation, the second one instead fixing the temperature fluctuation amplitude. One can imagine that there could be a single indicator $g = g(\Delta T, \omega)$ governing the transition from the condition of single flame to multiple flames and that using only this parameter we can take into account the multiple variation of ΔT and ω . Fig. 9

Figure 7: First and second critical temperature amplitudes, ΔT_{c1} and ΔT_{c2} , as function of the inlet temperature. The two critical temperature amplitudes, ΔT_{c1} and ΔT_{c2} , and their respective lower and upper bounds are plotted as a function of the normalized inlet temperature θ . Low inlet temperatures facilitate transition to nonlinear behavior.

Figure 8: First critical temperature amplitude ΔT_{c1} as function of the Strouhal number. The first critical temperature amplitude is computed as function of the normalized inlet temperature θ and the Strouhal number St . Small inlet temperatures and high excitation frequencies promote the occurrence of multiple flames. This means that even small inlet excitations can trigger nonlinear phenomena.

Figure 9: Region of multiple flame front occurrence as a function of excitation amplitude and Strouhal number. For a given normalized inlet temperature θ we present in light red the linear conditions where no multiple flames are observed. The map shows how the transition to multiple flames region happens for smaller temperature excitations in the high frequency range.

Figure 10: Backward-facing step used for LES simulations, figure adapted from Bothien *et al.* [14].

presents the isolines of $g = g(\Delta T, \omega)$ for different inlet temperatures, or in other terms the boundaries between single-flame and multiple-flames conditions. System states below the isoline $g = g(\Delta T, \omega)$ represent single flame conditions, whereas system states above $g = g(\Delta T, \omega)$ represent multiple flame conditions.

4. Numerical validation

To validate the results of the analytic model compressible LES conducted previously by Bothien *et al.* [14] is used. The simple one dimensional duct considered in Section §2 is replaced by a backward-facing step (BFS). This is a simplified model of a reheat combustor. The flame behavior in the vicinity of the axis is still very close to what we would expect in a simple duct. The geometrical layout is presented in Fig. 10. The step height S controls the size of the recirculation zone [33] and, together with the mean flow velocity \bar{u} , reproduces typical Reynolds number of gas

turbines combustors. The combustor length L guarantees that the chemistry reaches an equilibrium condition.

4.1. Numerical setup and combustion model

Compressible LES in [14] are performed by means of the commercial software ANSYS Fluent v17.0. The mesh consists of 2.11 million hexahedral cells, refined at the step and flame locations to better resolve the chemistry and the fluid dynamics. The LES overall mesh quality is judged by a quality index [34], which represents the ratio between the resolved turbulent kinetic energy (resolved TKE) and the overall turbulent kinetic energy (subgrid TKE + resolved TKE). The quality index is set to be higher than 0.85, resulting in less than 0.5 % of the total mesh cells to have a value lower than this threshold, and these are located far downstream of the flame. A second order spatial and temporal discretization scheme is used for all transported quantities, except for the momentum equation which uses the bounded central difference scheme. The constant time step used for the implicit solver provides a convective Courant number less than 1.5 in the domain. Turbulence scales larger than the mesh size are computed, whereas the Smagorinsky-Lilly subgrid-scale model with dynamic stress, dynamic energy flux, and a Prandtl number of 0.85 has been used to characterize the smaller scales. The turbulent Schmidt number is set to 0.7 for scalar flux and for species.

The bottom wall is an adiabatic, no-slip wall, whereas the top one is a stationary wall with zero shear stress and zero heat flux. Therefore a boundary layer will be developed only in the bottom part of the simulation domain. Periodic boundary conditions are applied to the side surfaces. At the inlet fully premixed conditions prevent effects of mixture inhomogeneities on the flame dynamics. The outlet is set to a non-reflecting boundary condition to avoid acoustic waves reflection and possible thermoacoustic instabilities.

The combustion is modeled with the method developed by Kulkarni *et al.* [35, 36, 37], relying on tabulated chemistry. Homogeneous reactor simulations are performed and quantities of interest are recorded. In addition, a progress variable is computed, to represent the chemistry development history. The combustion model solves the transport equation of the mixture fraction and of the composite progress variable, which takes into account the intermediate species and products, relying on the homogeneous reactor simulations results. The inlet mixture consists of air perfectly premixed with methane treated as an ideal gas. For more information about the geometrical setup, the numerical mesh and the combustion model, the reader is referred to Bothien *et al.* [14].

4.2. Simulation description and results

In Section §3.3 two parameters are considered to be responsible for the transition from a single flame configuration to multiple flames, the temperature fluctuations

Figure 11: Region of multiple flame fronts occurrence as a function of the Strouhal number for LES simulations. Above the black line the system exhibits multiple flames. With red crosses we highlight the six different simulations i.e., $St = 0.44$ and $\Delta T/\bar{T} = 0.49, 1.11, 2.28, 2.9, 3.41, 4.92\%$.

amplitude ΔT and the angular frequency of excitation ω . Here we have chosen for simplicity to consider the latter fixed to a given value $\bar{\omega}$ and to study the system transition as ΔT increases. We perform six different simulations, exciting sinusoidally the inlet temperature at a Strouhal number $St = 0.44$ with increasing temperature fluctuation amplitudes from approximately 0.5% to 5%. We choose exactly the same values reported in Bothien *et al.* [14].

In Fig. 11, six points at $St = 0.44$ corresponding to the simulations states are shown. Additionally, the theoretical transition curve from single to multiple flame conditions, given in Eq. (11), is depicted. From the plot, it is expected that the three simulations with larger inlet temperature fluctuations show nonlinear effects. We reproduce in Fig. 12 a result of Bothien *et al.* [14], where the heat release rate fluctuation amplitude is presented as function of the harmonic temperature excitation. The transition from linear to nonlinear behavior is found at around 2.5% of the inlet excitation amplitude. This is in very good agreement with the one dimensional model prediction of Fig. 11.

Figure 13 shows results over a cycle of inlet temperature excitation, for three of the six excitation conditions depicted in Fig. 11. The analytically computed flame position is compared to the one extracted from LES. The corresponding heat release rate fluctuations are reported in Fig. 14, where the peaks in energy release are associated to the sudden flashback of the flame front (case A and B) and to the appearance of multiple flame fronts (case C). Both Fig. 13 and Fig. 14 present a nonlinear behavior around a phase of 2π , especially for simulations B and C. The same results are presented also in Fig. 15, where the colormap allows the visualization of the upcoming temperature wave to the flame front. The flame position is identified by the black isocontour lines, that enclose an area where the heat release is larger than a given threshold. The predictions

Figure 12: Normalized heat release rate fluctuation amplitude as a function of the amplitude of the harmonic temperature excitation at $St = 0.44$. The values of the simulated temperature amplitudes are reported in the top x axis. Figure reproduced from Bothien *et al.* [14].

Figure 13: Comparison between flame position predicted with the one dimensional model (lines) and the LES results (symbols). Three different excitation conditions are reported: $\Delta T/\bar{T} = 1.11\%$ (A), 2.28% (B), 4.92% (C). The latter condition shows, for a part of the period, multiple squares for the same time instant, i.e. multiple flame fronts. The model capability to reproduce the flame front oscillation is good for small excitations, becoming less accurate for larger ones. This is mainly due to the neglect of flame propagation and temperature diffusion.

Figure 14: Normalized heat release rate over two excitation periods for three excitation conditions: $\Delta T/\bar{T} = 1.11\%$ (A), 2.28% (B), 4.92% (C).

stemming from the one dimensional model are shown with vertical white segments on the top of each frame.

For the first two columns, the excitation amplitudes are $\Delta T/\bar{T} = 1.11\%$ and $\Delta T/\bar{T} = 2.28\%$ respectively. Qualitatively the same behavior is observed. Starting from 0° and increasing the phase the flame moves downstream in the combustor. This is related to a locally colder stream impinging on the flame front. A cold spot is convected along the domain. The lower temperatures result in lower autoignition delay times and therefore shift the flame position downstream. Starting from 250° the unburnt mixture just upstream of the flame location gets hotter (because of the imposed change in inlet temperature) causing the flame to bounce back. Again, physically this is due to the change in autoignition delay time. The one dimensional model predictions for the given inlet mixture properties and temperature profile are presented with the continuous white vertical line. The furthest upstream flame position is correctly captured, whereas the velocity at which the flame moves downstream and the furthest downstream flame position are slightly overpredicted. Different physical phenomena not captured in the model can explain this behavior. Flame propagation is probably the most important: the flame tends to propagate in the unburnt mixture and this sums up with the change in autoignition delay time to give a smaller effective velocity. This also explains why the furthest downstream flame position is not captured but the bounce back is (plot for 350°). Another phenomenon is diffusion: as the fluid is convected, hot spots tend to diffuse and therefore effective smaller amplitude temperature fluctuations should be considered. Diffusion gets more and more important for larger ΔT . Finally, also the presence of the BFS is impacting the results. The flow slows down after the area expansion and therefore the chemistry has more time to evolve than in the ideal constant-velocity case. A more accurate model to take into account the presence of the BFS and velocity

nonuniformities in general would be:

$$x_{\text{fl}}(t + \tau(t)) = \int_t^{t+\tau(t)} u(t') dt' \quad (16)$$

where x_{fl} is the flame front location. This could significantly improve also the second and third flame position predictions.

Observing the flame dynamics presented in the first two columns it can be noticed how the flame slowly moves downstream in the first part of the oscillation period, whereas when the mixture gets hotter it suddenly bounces back. In a small amount of time a large quantity of fresh gases is burnt, this results in a high heat release rate. This phenomenon provides a physical explanation for the high gains typically observed in past studies on autoignition flames, see [13, 14, 20].

The third column presents the nonlinear case for $\Delta T/\bar{T} = 4.92\%$. Again, starting from 0° phase angle the flame moves downstream due to lower unburnt mixture temperatures. The model is overpredicting the velocity at which this phenomenon happens, as for the $\Delta T/\bar{T} = 1.11\%$ and $\Delta T/\bar{T} = 2.28\%$ cases. The difference now is that, for a phase of 300° , the flame is still exposed to a low temperature but, at the same time, a hot spot has just entered the combustor and begun to burn. Therefore two additional flame fronts are created at the combustor inlet, one remaining attached to the BFS and the other one travelling downstream in the unburnt mixture. A pocket of unburnt gas is convected along the combustor as can be observed in the 325° , 350° and 0° phase plots.

5. Conclusion

In this paper, the nonlinear phenomena occurring in autoignition flames forced with temperature fluctuations are discussed. The modulation of inlet temperature generates entropy inhomogeneities convected along the combustor. Given the high sensitivity of the autoignition delay time on temperature fluctuations, the flame starts to oscillate around a mean position, following the time evolution of inlet conditions after a delay given by the convective time. The phenomenon becomes nonlinear even for moderate excitation amplitudes, generating multiple flames simultaneously co-existing.

A simple one dimensional analytic model is derived helping to understand the phenomenon. Its mathematical properties are analyzed and limits for the occurrence of multiple flame conditions are given. Critical temperature amplitudes and oscillation frequencies are defined, separating characteristic regions. Using correlations from the GRI 3.0 chemistry mechanism the theory is concretized into practical maps. Limits of application are pointed out and related to model simplifications. The theoretical results are compared with LES simulations conducted on a simplified geometry. The capability of the model to predict the presence of multiple flames and nonlinearities is

Figure 15: Temperature contour plots for the BFS simulations for different time instants. Each column represents a single simulation: $\Delta T/\bar{T} = 1.11\%$ (A), 2.28% (B), 4.92% (C). The rows present LES results at different phase angles of one oscillation period, as indicated on the left. The flame position, obtained as the area where the heat release is larger than a given threshold, is given by the black contour line separating the unburnt cold mixture from the hot combustion products. The prediction of the flame front position from the one dimensional model is presented by the vertical white segments above each screenshot. The temperature at the inlet of the domain is excited sinusoidally and this is reflected in a motion of the flame front, from an upstream condition for high unburnt gases temperature (0° phase), to a downstream condition for low temperatures (250° phase). Nonlinearities appear and pockets of unburnt gases can detach and be convected along the combustor. A video representation of this figure can be found online as supplementary material.

verified. This allows us to estimate the inlet temperature forcing limits to remain in the linear field without the necessity of performing time consuming, computationally expensive simulations with increasing amplitude disturbances, as done up to now [14, 20]. Additionally, it is shown that the flame position can be qualitatively estimated, even if propagation and diffusion phenomena are not taken into account.

In future works, the nonlinear flame behavior arising already before the occurrence of multiple flame fronts will be investigated. In addition to this, a model of the BFS could lead to a quantitative prediction of LES results and would ultimately provide more in-depth physical insight. Experimental investigations of these nonlinear characteristics and their interaction with the acoustic field in a more realistic configuration is also needed.

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References

- [1] F. Güthe, J. Hellat, P. Flohr, [The Reheat Concept: The Proven Pathway to Ultralow Emissions and High Efficiency and Flexibility](#), *Journal of Engineering for Gas Turbines and Power* 131 (2). doi:10.1115/1.2836613. URL <http://GasTurbinesPower.asmedigitalcollection.asme.org/article.aspx?articleid=1474556>
- [2] K. M. Düsing, A. Ciani, U. Benz, A. Eroglu, K. Knapp, [Development of GT24 and GT26 \(Upgrades 2011\) Reheat Combustors, Achieving Reduced Emissions and Increased Fuel Flexibility](#), in: Volume 1B: Combustion, Fuels and Emissions, paper no. GT2013-95437, ASME, San Antonio, Texas, USA, 2013. doi:10.1115/GT2013-95437. URL <http://proceedings.asmedigitalcollection.asme.org/proceeding.aspx?doi=10.1115/GT2013-95437>
- [3] D. A. Pennell, M. R. Bothien, A. Ciani, V. Granet, G. Singla, S. Thorpe, A. Wickstroem, K. Oumejjoud, M. Yaquinto, [An Introduction to the Ansaldo GT36 Constant Pressure Sequential Combustor](#), in: Volume 4B: Combustion, Fuels and Emissions, paper no. GT2017-64790, ASME, Charlotte, North Carolina, USA, 2017. doi:10.1115/GT2017-64790. URL <http://proceedings.asmedigitalcollection.asme.org/proceeding.aspx?doi=10.1115/GT2017-64790>
- [4] M. Bothien, A. Ciani, J. Wood, G. Fruechtel, [Sequential Combustion in Gas Turbines – the Key Technology for Burning High Hydrogen Contents with Low Emissions](#), in: Combustion, Fuels and Emissions, paper no. GT2019-90798, ASME, Phoenix, Arizona, USA, 2019. URL <https://www.asmeconferences.org/TE2019/PaperAccepted.cfm?noToolbar=yes>
- [5] A. Huber, W. Polifke, [Dynamics of Practical Premixed Flames, Part I: Model Structure and Identification](#), *International Journal of Spray and Combustion Dynamics* 1 (2) (2009) 199–228. doi:10.1260/175682709788707431. URL <http://journals.sagepub.com/doi/10.1260/175682709788707431>
- [6] A. Huber, W. Polifke, [Dynamics of Practical Premixed Flames, Part II: Identification and Interpretation of CFD Data](#), *International Journal of Spray and Combustion Dynamics* 1 (2) (2009) 229–249. doi:10.1260/175682709788707440. URL <http://journals.sagepub.com/doi/10.1260/175682709788707440>
- [7] L. Boyer, J. Quinard, [On the dynamics of anchored flames](#), *Combustion and Flame* 82 (1) (1990) 51–65. doi:10.1016/0010-2180(90)90077-5. URL <http://linkinghub.elsevier.com/retrieve/pii/S0010218090900775>
- [8] C. J. Lawn, S. Evesque, W. Polifke, [A model for the thermoacoustic response of a premixed swirl burner, part I: acoustic aspects](#), *Combustion Science and Technology* 176 (8) (2004) 1331–1358. doi:10.1080/00102200490461605. URL <http://www.tandfonline.com/doi/abs/10.1080/00102200490461605>
- [9] C. J. Lawn, W. Polifke, [A model for the thermoacoustic response of a premixed swirl burner, part II: the flame response](#), *Combustion Science and Technology* 176 (8) (2004) 1359–1390. doi:10.1080/00102200490461623. URL <http://www.tandfonline.com/doi/abs/10.1080/00102200490461623>
- [10] D. You, Y. Huang, V. Yang, [A generalized model of acoustic response of turbulent premixed flame and its application to gas-turbine combustion instability analysis](#), *Combustion Science and Technology* 177 (5-6) (2005) 1109–1150. doi:10.1080/00102200590927012. URL <http://www.tandfonline.com/doi/abs/10.1080/00102200590927012>
- [11] B. Schuermans, V. Bellucci, F. Guethe, F. Meili, P. Flohr, C. O. Paschereit, [A Detailed Analysis of Thermoacoustic Interaction Mechanisms in a Turbulent Premixed Flame](#), in: Volume 1: Turbo Expo 2004, paper no. GT2004-53831, ASME, Vienna, Austria, 2004, pp. 539–551. doi:10.1115/GT2004-53831. URL <http://proceedings.asmedigitalcollection.asme.org/proceeding.aspx?articleid=1636336>
- [12] B. Čosić, S. Terhaar, J. P. Moeck, C. O. Paschereit, [Response of a swirl-stabilized flame to simultaneous perturbations in equivalence ratio and velocity at high oscillation amplitudes](#), *Combustion and Flame* 162 (4) (2015) 1046–1062. doi:10.1016/j.combustflame.2014.09.025. URL <https://linkinghub.elsevier.com/retrieve/pii/S001021801400306X>
- [13] A. Scarpatto, L. Zander, R. Kulkarni, B. Schuermans, [Identification of Multi-Parameter Flame Transfer Function for a Reheat Combustor](#), in: Volume 4B: Combustion, Fuels and Emissions, paper no. GT2016-57699, ASME, Seoul, South Korea, 2016. doi:10.1115/GT2016-57699. URL <http://proceedings.asmedigitalcollection.asme.org/proceeding.aspx?doi=10.1115/GT2016-57699>
- [14] M. Bothien, D. Lauper, Y. Yang, A. Scarpatto, [Reconstruction and Analysis of the Acoustic Transfer Matrix of a Reheat Flame From Large-Eddy Simulations](#), *Journal of Engineering for Gas Turbines and Power* 141 (2). doi:10.1115/1.4041151. URL <http://gasturbinespower.asmedigitalcollection.asme.org/article.aspx?doi=10.1115/1.4041151>
- [15] M. Zellhuber, B. Schuermans, W. Polifke, [Impact of acoustic pressure on autoignition and heat release](#), *Combustion Theory and Modelling* 18 (1) (2014) 1–31. doi:10.1080/13647830.2013.817609. URL <http://www.tandfonline.com/doi/abs/10.1080/13647830.2013.817609>
- [16] M. Zellhuber, J. Schwing, B. Schuermans, T. Sattelmayer, W. Polifke, [Experimental and Numerical Investigation of Thermoacoustic Sources Related to High-Frequency Instabilities](#), *International Journal of Spray and Combustion Dynamics* 6 (1) (2014) 1–34. doi:10.1260/1756-8277.6.1.1. URL <http://journals.sagepub.com/doi/10.1260/1756-8277.6.1.1>
- [17] Y. Yang, N. Noiray, A. Scarpatto, O. Schulz, K. M. Düsing, M. Bothien, [Numerical Analysis of the Dynamic Flame Response in Alstom Reheat Combustion Systems](#), in: Volume 4A: Combustion, Fuels and Emissions, paper no. GT2015-

- 42622, ASME, Montreal, Quebec, Canada, 2015. doi:10.1115/GT2015-42622.
URL <http://proceedings.asmedigitalcollection.asme.org/proceeding.aspx?doi=10.1115/GT2015-42622>
- [18] K. Aditya, A. Gruber, C. Xu, T. Lu, A. Krisman, M. R. Bothien, J. H. Chen, **Direct numerical simulation of flame stabilization assisted by autoignition in a reheat gas turbine combustor**, Proceedings of the Combustion Institute 37 (2) (2018) 2635–2642. doi:10.1016/j.proci.2018.06.084.
URL <https://linkinghub.elsevier.com/retrieve/pii/S1540748918302670>
- [19] O. Schulz, T. Jaravel, T. Poinso, B. Cuenot, N. Noiray, **A criterion to distinguish autoignition and propagation applied to a lifted methane–air jet flame**, Proceedings of the Combustion Institute 36 (2) (2017) 1637–1644. doi:10.1016/j.proci.2016.08.022.
URL <https://linkinghub.elsevier.com/retrieve/pii/S1540748916304114>
- [20] O. Schulz, U. Doll, D. Ebi, J. Droujko, C. Bourquard, N. Noiray, **Thermoacoustic instability in a sequential combustor: Large eddy simulation and experiments**, Proceedings of the Combustion Institute 37 (4) (2019) 5325–5332. doi:10.1016/j.proci.2018.07.089.
URL <https://linkinghub.elsevier.com/retrieve/pii/S1540748918305078>
- [21] J. M. Fleck, P. Griebel, A. M. Steinberg, M. Stöhr, M. Aigner, A. Ciani, **Experimental Investigation of a Generic, Fuel Flexible Reheat Combustor at Gas Turbine Relevant Operating Conditions**, in: Volume 2: Combustion, Fuels and Emissions, paper no. GT2010-22722, ASME, Glasgow, UK, 2010, pp. 583–592. doi:10.1115/GT2010-22722.
URL <http://proceedings.asmedigitalcollection.asme.org/proceeding.aspx?articleid=1608176>
- [22] J. Fleck, P. Griebel, A. Steinberg, M. Stöhr, M. Aigner, A. Ciani, **Autoignition Limits of Hydrogen at Relevant Reheat Combustor Operating Conditions**, Journal of Engineering for Gas Turbines and Power 134 (4). doi:10.1115/1.4004500.
URL <http://GasTurbinesPower.asmedigitalcollection.asme.org/article.aspx?articleid=1429827>
- [23] J. M. Fleck, P. Griebel, A. M. Steinberg, C. M. Arndt, C. Naumann, M. Aigner, **Autoignition of hydrogen/nitrogen jets in vitiated air crossflows at different pressures**, Proceedings of the Combustion Institute 34 (2) (2013) 3185–3192. doi:10.1016/j.proci.2012.05.039.
URL <http://linkinghub.elsevier.com/retrieve/pii/S1540748912000405>
- [24] J. Eckstein, E. Freitag, C. Hirsch, T. Sattelmayer, **Experimental Study on the Role of Entropy Waves in Low-Frequency Oscillations in a RQL Combustor**, Journal of Engineering for Gas Turbines and Power 128 (2) (2006) 264–270. doi:10.1115/1.2132379.
URL <http://GasTurbinesPower.asmedigitalcollection.asme.org/article.aspx?articleid=1423629>
- [25] A. Giusti, N. A. Worth, E. Mastorakos, A. P. Dowling, **Experimental and Numerical Investigation into the Propagation of Entropy Waves**, AIAA Journal 55 (2) (2017) 446–458. doi:10.2514/1.J055199.
URL <https://arc.aiaa.org/doi/10.2514/1.J055199>
- [26] L. Li, D. Zhao, X. Yang, **Effect of entropy waves on transient energy growth of flow disturbances in triggering thermoacoustic instability**, International Journal of Heat and Mass Transfer 99 (2016) 219–233. doi:10.1016/j.ijheatmasstransfer.2016.03.084.
URL <https://linkinghub.elsevier.com/retrieve/pii/S0017931015312102>
- [27] L. Magri, J. O’Brien, M. Ihme, **Compositional inhomogeneities as a source of indirect combustion noise**, Journal of Fluid Mechanics 799. doi:10.1017/jfm.2016.397.
URL http://www.journals.cambridge.org/abstract_S0022112016003979
- [28] L. Magri, **On indirect noise in multicomponent nozzle flows**, Journal of Fluid Mechanics 828. doi:10.1017/jfm.2017.591.
URL https://www.cambridge.org/core/product/identifier/S0022112017005912/type/journal_article
- [29] Y. Pei, M. Mehl, W. Liu, T. Lu, W. J. Pitz, S. Som, **A Multi-component Blend as a Diesel Fuel Surrogate for Compression Ignition Engine Applications**, Journal of Engineering for Gas Turbines and Power 137 (11). doi:10.1115/1.4030416.
URL <http://gasturbinespower.asmedigitalcollection.asme.org/article.aspx?doi=10.1115/1.4030416>
- [30] M. A. Oehlschlaeger, J. Steinberg, C. K. Westbrook, W. J. Pitz, **The autoignition of iso-cetane at high to moderate temperatures and elevated pressures: Shock tube experiments and kinetic modeling**, Combustion and Flame 156 (11) (2009) 2165–2172. doi:10.1016/j.combustflame.2009.05.007.
URL <http://linkinghub.elsevier.com/retrieve/pii/S0010218009001436>
- [31] W. J. Pitz, C. J. Mueller, **Recent progress in the development of diesel surrogate fuels**, Progress in Energy and Combustion Science 37 (3) (2011) 330–350. doi:10.1016/j.pecs.2010.06.004.
URL <http://linkinghub.elsevier.com/retrieve/pii/S0360128510000535>
- [32] M. Frenklach, H. Wang, M. Goldenberg, G. Smith, D. Golden, C. Bowman, R. Hanson, W. Gardiner, V. Lissianski, GRI-Mech An Optimized Detailed Chemical Reaction Mechanism for Methane Combustion.
- [33] G. Biswas, M. Breuer, F. Durst, **Backward-Facing Step Flows for Various Expansion Ratios at Low and Moderate Reynolds Numbers**, Journal of Fluids Engineering 126 (3) (2004) 362–374. doi:10.1115/1.1760532.
URL <http://FluidsEngineering.asmedigitalcollection.asme.org/article.aspx?articleid=1429967>
- [34] I. Celik, M. Klein, J. Janicka, **Assessment Measures for Engineering LES Applications**, Journal of Fluids Engineering 131 (3). doi:10.1115/1.3059703.
URL <http://FluidsEngineering.asmedigitalcollection.asme.org/article.aspx?articleid=1478229>
- [35] R. Kulkarni, B. Bunkute, F. Biagioli, M. Duesing, W. Polifke, **Large Eddy Simulation of ALSTOM’s Reheat Combustor Using Tabulated Chemistry and Stochastic Fields-Combustion Model**, in: Volume 4B: Combustion, Fuels and Emissions, paper no. GT2014-26053, ASME, Düsseldorf, Germany, 2014. doi:10.1115/GT2014-26053.
URL <http://proceedings.asmedigitalcollection.asme.org/proceeding.aspx?doi=10.1115/GT2014-26053>
- [36] R. M. Kulkarni, W. Polifke, **LES of Delft-Jet-In-Hot-Coflow (DJHC) with tabulated chemistry and stochastic fields combustion model**, Fuel Processing Technology 107 (2013) 138–146. doi:10.1016/j.fuproc.2012.06.015.
URL <https://linkinghub.elsevier.com/retrieve/pii/S0378382012002275>
- [37] R. Kulkarni, **Large eddy simulation of autoignition in turbulent flows**, PhD thesis, Technische Universität München (2013).

Appendix A. Mathematical demonstration of the first critical temperature oscillation equation

We want to prove Eq. (11), i.e. that necessary and sufficient condition for the existence of multiple flame fronts is that it exists $\bar{X} \in [0, 2\pi/\omega]$ so that $\frac{dF_x(X)}{dX}\Big|_{\bar{X}} = \frac{\partial F(X,Y)}{\partial X}\Big|_{\bar{X}} > 0$. In other words we want to show that, if

$$\frac{dF_x(X)}{dX} = \frac{\partial F(X,Y)}{\partial X} < 0 \quad \forall X \in [0, 2\pi/\omega] \quad (\text{A.1})$$

then there is only one flame front for each time instant Y . If, conversely, there exists $\bar{X} \in [0, 2\pi/\omega]$ for which

$$\left. \frac{dF_x(X)}{dX} \right|_{\bar{X}} = \left. \frac{\partial F(X, Y)}{\partial X} \right|_{\bar{X}} > 0 \quad \bar{X} \in [0, 2\pi/\omega] \quad (\text{A.2})$$

then it is always possible to find a time instant $Y \in [0, 2\pi/\omega]$ for which two flame fronts are present. Additionally we also want to prove that Eq. (12) holds, i.e. that there exists an upper bound for the solution of Eq. (11) and that this is given by the solution of:

$$\tau_{\max} - \tau_{\min} = \frac{\pi}{\omega} \quad (\text{12})$$

We start by assuming that:

$$\tau_{\max} - \tau_{\min} \geq \frac{\pi}{\omega} \quad (\text{A.3})$$

In this case it is easy to show that there exists a time instant $Y \in [0, 2\pi/\omega]$ for which there are two flame fronts. This time instant Y is given by $Y = 0$. In fact for $Y = 0$ there are at least two flames. One is located at $X_{\text{fl}} = 0$:

$$\begin{aligned} F(X_{\text{fl}} = 0, Y = 0) &= \tau(\bar{T} + \Delta T \cos(\omega_0)) - \tau_{\min} - X_{\text{fl}} + Y \\ &= \tau(\bar{T} + \Delta T) - \tau_{\min} = 0 \end{aligned} \quad (\text{A.4})$$

The second one is located at $X_{\text{fl}} = \bar{X} \in (0, \pi/\omega]$. The presence of the second zero is assured by Bolzano theorem. We consider a closed interval $[\Delta X, \pi/\omega]$ with $0 < \Delta X < \pi/\omega$ and we show that the continuous function $F(X, 0)$ assumes opposite signs values at its extremes. We cannot consider as left end of the interval $X = 0$, because $F(X = 0, 0) = 0$. The choice of a sufficiently small $\Delta X = X - X_0$ is therefore necessary. Expanding $F(X, 0)$ in series around $X_0 = 0$:

$$\begin{aligned} F(X_0 + \Delta X, Y = 0) &= F(X_0, 0) + \dots \\ &+ \left. \frac{dF(X, Y = 0)}{dX} \right|_{(X=X_0)} \Delta X + \dots \\ &\approx \left. \frac{dF(X, 0)}{dX} \right|_{(X=X_0)} \Delta X \\ &= -\Delta X < 0 \end{aligned} \quad (\text{A.5})$$

In the last passage we used the property that $\left. \frac{dF(X, 0)}{dX} \right|_{(X=0)} = \left. \frac{dF_x(X)}{dX} \right|_{(X=0)} = -1$. This is easily verified starting from the definition of $F_x(X)$, Eq. (10). Equation (A.5) shows that for a sufficiently small ΔX , $F(\Delta X, 0)$ is negative. Let's now evaluate $F(X, 0)$ at the other end of the interval:

$$\begin{aligned} F(\pi/\omega, Y = 0) &= \tau(\bar{T} + \Delta T \cos(\pi)) - \tau_{\min} - \pi/\omega \\ &= \tau(\bar{T} - \Delta T) - \tau_{\min} - \pi/\omega \\ &= \tau_{\max} - \tau_{\min} - \pi/\omega \geq 0 \end{aligned} \quad (\text{A.6})$$

Last equality of Eq. (A.6) is a consequence of Eq. (A.3). If $F(\pi/\omega, Y = 0)$ is strictly positive, then Bolzano theorem

applies and there will be a zero of $F(X, 0)$ in the interval $[\Delta X, \pi/\omega]$. If instead $F(\pi/\omega, Y = 0) = 0$, then the second zero is located exactly at $X = \pi/\omega$. This shows that if Eq. (A.3) is satisfied, then there are always at least two flame fronts.

To verify eqs. (A.1) and (A.2) we consider the opposite situation, i.e.:

$$\tau_{\max} - \tau_{\min} < \frac{\pi}{\omega} \quad (\text{A.7})$$

We show first that if $\left. \frac{dF_x(X)}{dX} \right|_{\bar{X}} = \left. \frac{\partial F(X, Y)}{\partial X} \right|_{\bar{X}} < 0 \quad \forall X \in [0, 2\pi/\omega]$ then there cannot be two flames. This condition mathematically is expressed by the fact that $F(X, Y)$ has at most a single zero in the interval $[0, 2\pi/\omega]$ for each $Y \in [0, 2\pi/\omega]$. Equation (A.1) implies that $F_x(X)$ is strictly monotonic in X . A corollary of the intermediate value theorem for strictly monotonic function assures us that $F_x(X)$ will assume exactly once each value between $F_x(X = 0) = 0$ and $F_x(X = 2\pi/\omega) = \tau_{\max} - \tau_{\min} - 2\pi/\omega < 0$. This means that, fixed $Y \in [0, 2\pi/\omega)$, there will be exactly one X for which $F(X, Y) = 0$.

We consider now the condition expressed by Eq. (A.2). We want to show that there exists a time instant $\bar{Y} \in [0, 2\pi/\omega]$ for which $F(X, \bar{Y})$ has at least two zeros. We arbitrarily choose:

$$\bar{Y} = -\tau(\bar{T} + \Delta T \cos(\omega \bar{X})) - \tau_{\min} + \bar{X} \quad (\text{A.8})$$

Therefore we fix the time to a given value. For this value we want to show that there are multiple flame fronts. We evaluate now $F(X = \bar{X}, \bar{Y})$:

$$F(\bar{X}, \bar{Y}) = (\tau(\bar{T} + \Delta T \cos(\omega \bar{X})) + \tau_{\min} - \bar{X}) - \bar{Y} = 0 \quad (\text{A.9})$$

We have therefore found that, for this choice of the time Y , there is a flame located at \bar{X} . We expand in series $F(X, \bar{Y})$ around \bar{X} :

$$\begin{aligned} F(X, \bar{Y}) &= F(\bar{X}, \bar{Y}) + \left. \frac{\partial F(X, \bar{Y})}{\partial X} \right|_{\bar{X}} (X - \bar{X}) + \dots \\ &\approx \left. \frac{\partial F(X, \bar{Y})}{\partial X} \right|_{\bar{X}} (X - \bar{X}) \end{aligned} \quad (\text{A.10})$$

We consider now the coordinate $X = \bar{X} + \Delta X$. For a sufficiently small $\Delta X > 0$:

$$F(\bar{X} + \Delta X, \bar{Y}) = \left. \frac{\partial F(X, \bar{Y})}{\partial X} \right|_{\bar{X}} \Delta X > 0 \quad (\text{A.11})$$

because $\left. \frac{\partial F(X, \bar{Y})}{\partial X} \right|_{\bar{X}} > 0$ per hypothesis. Therefore in the interval $[\bar{X} + \Delta X, 2\pi/\omega]$ the function $F(X, \bar{Y})$ must have a zero (Bolzano theorem), remembering that $F(2\pi/\omega, \bar{Y}) < 0$. The same reasoning can be applied to the interval $[0, \bar{X} - \Delta X]$, showing the presence of a third flame front.